

Skin Disease Detection Using a Robust Hybrid Deep Learning Model¹

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Abstract

Skin diseases are a global health concern and require early and accurate diagnosis. This research work proposed a hybrid deep learning based intelligent system, which detects skin diseases with higher accuracy and precision. The proposed model implements image preprocessing such as image resizing, Gaussian blurring (using a 3x3 filter), contrast enhancement, sharpening techniques, and Holistically Nested Edge detection (HNED) for image segmentation. EfficientNet B0 is used to extract the 1280 features from the image and represented in a 1D array. Further, this projected pipeline is used in the proposed model RMCNN-LSTM, which extracts the spatial as well as the temporal features from the images. The model is implemented on the Dermnet dataset and achieves a training accuracy of 94% and a validation accuracy of 80%. This validation accuracy results in the model depicting that the model diagnosis skin diseases at a high accuracy rate at early stages.

Keywords

Skin Diseases, Image Preprocessing, Deep Learning, Hybrid Model, Dermnet Dataset, Classification, Prediction

1. Introduction

Skin is the outermost part and largest organ of the human body, which generally weighs 3.5 kg in the hands of a fully grown adult. Skin consists of three layers: dermis, epidermis and hypodermis [1] and protect us in many ways, such as regulating body temperature, permitting the sensation of touch, heat and cold. In spite of taking as much care, human skin is most prone to infections due to its direct contact with the environment. It is affected by various factors such as viruses, fungi, bacteria, sports activities,

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lack of a strong immune system, genetic imbalances and working environment. These factors not only affect the skin's function but also damage the skin to some greater extent and can threaten human life in severe cases[2]. Skin diseases like psoriasis and eczema may cause chronic sleep loss and horrible symptoms of redness and scaling that affect self-esteem and self-confidence. Skin cancer is the most common cancer worldwide, and is categorised into two types, i.e. benign and melanoma. Basal cell carcinoma is the most frequent, whereas melanoma is the deadliest skin cancer[3]. Skin conditions also lead to anxiety, chronic stress, depression and become more dangerous as time passes. As a result, early and accurate diagnosis of skin diseases is very important. Many advanced technologies have solved the problem of diagnosing skin diseases at early stages with perfection. Still, these technologies are very costly, limited and not within reach of the general people. Hence, there is a need to develop an automated model to detect skin diseases at an early stage with higher accuracy[4]. Artificial intelligence[5], machine learning[6] and deep learning[7] technologies have solved the problem of early diagnosis of skin diseases by introducing various novel systems. These intelligent systems can analyse dermatological images and identify patterns associated with different skin conditions. The development of automated diagnostic tools has the potential to support dermatologists, improve diagnostic accuracy, and facilitate early detection of skin diseases. Therefore, research in this area aims to integrate advanced computational techniques with medical knowledge to develop reliable and efficient systems for skin disease detection and classification.

Table 1: Dermnet dataset samples on which the hybrid model is implemented[8]

Acne	Dermatitis	Eczema	Impetigo	Alopecia	Psoriasis

The main motivation of this study is to develop a hybrid model that improves the classification accuracy. Deep learning based models have shown great results in predicting skin diseases, but often fail to balance the transparency with predictive performance, which is crucial for clinical adoption. Although most of the deep learning methodologies rely on a single architecture, this restricts the capability of the model to capture multiple aspects of dermatological data. Hybridization of different architectures, such as CNNs and RNNs, has the potential to address these gaps.

This research paper is organized in the following ways: Section 2 describes the related works, in brief, which compares the various datasets used by the researchers. The next section covers the dataset description, and further materials and methodology are described in brief. Lastly, experimental results are discussed with the conclusion of the paper.

2. Related Works:

There are millions of people worldwide who suffer from skin diseases, and thus it is a great public health issue. It is very important to diagnose skin diseases accurately and in a timely manner for effective treatment and prevention. Dermatologists have always used traditional methods like visual inspection,

which can be lengthy and subjective when diagnosing skin diseases. Automation of these techniques through computer vision and deep learning has made great progress in recent years. Such methods will enhance precision, efficiency, and accessibility in the process of diagnosing this condition (especially since most individuals cannot just walk into a doctor's office whenever they feel like).

Convolutional neural networks provide the relationship between input images and their class labels. CNNs are mostly used for image recognition and classification. Various CNNs based architecture were used for skin disease detection, which are available in the literature survey. Researchers have combined various machine learning and deep learning methodologies, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), K- nearest neighbour(k-NN), Decision Trees (DT), Random Forest (RF), with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), VGG-16, ResNet- 50 for classification purposes. In this paper, the proposed model classifies the skin diseases based on Dermnet data [9][10][11][12][13][14].

In [15] authors proposed a model for skin disease classification using image processing techniques. In this, on 50 sample images, fuzzy clustering is applied with KNN and SVM along with wavelet analysis. The presented approach with an accuracy of 91.2% identified the type of skin diseases. However, the problem was the model worked only for 50 sample images of two classes.

In[16] authors proposed a hybrid model that combines machine learning and deep learning for feature selection and classification. Deep neural network techniques such as Alexnet, Resnet50, GoogleNet, and VGG16 were used for feature selection, and machine learning-based techniques corresponding to Support Vector Machine, Ensemble Adaboost, and Decision Tree were used for classification.

Table 1: Comparison of available datasets used by various researchers

Dataset Name	Ref. No.	Year	No. of Images	Pros	Cons	Used By
DermNet (Kaggle)	[8]	2018	~19,500	Large dataset; 23 disease classes; real-world variability; publicly available	Class imbalance; varying image quality; limited annotations	CNN, EfficientNet models
HAM10000	[17]	2018	10,015	Well-annotated; dermoscopic images; widely benchmarked	Limited to pigmented lesions; fewer classes	CNN, ResNet, DenseNet
ISIC Archive	[18]	2016-ongoing	>25,000	High-quality labelled images; international standard dataset	Mostly melanoma-focused; class imbalance	Deep CNN, segmentation models
PH2 Dataset	[19]	2013	200	High-resolution images; expert annotations;	Very small dataset;	Traditional ML, CNN

				segmentation masks available	limited diversity	
Derm7pt	[20]	2018	~2,000	Includes clinical metadata; 7-point checklist features	Small size; limited disease variety	Multi-modal DL models
SD-198 Dataset	[21]	2019	6,584	Large number of disease classes (198); diverse conditions	Noisy labels; class imbalance	Multi-class classification models
PAD-UFES-20	[13]	2020	2,298	Includes patient metadata; clinical + dermoscopic images	Moderate dataset size; missing labels in some cases	Explainable AI, hybrid models

3. Dataset Description:

The dataset constitutes a fundamental component in the development and training of any intelligent system, particularly in deep learning applications where large volumes of data are essential for achieving optimal performance. A well-curated and standardized dataset significantly enhances the model's ability to generalize and produce reliable results. In this study, the DermNet dataset [8], sourced from the Kaggle repository, is utilized for experimental analysis. Table 2 describes the characteristics of Dermnet dataset. This dataset comprises approximately 19,500 clinical and dermoscopic images spanning 23 distinct categories of skin diseases, including acne, melanoma, eczema, psoriasis, and various fungal infections.

The images are available in RGB JPEG format and exhibit substantial variability in terms of quality and resolution, thereby reflecting real-world clinical conditions. Of the total dataset, nearly 15,500 images are allocated for training purposes, while around 4,000 images are reserved for validation. The diversity in disease categories, imaging conditions, and resolutions contributes to improved model robustness and supports the effective training of our proposed multi-class CNN–LSTM classifier. Furthermore, the use of a publicly accessible dataset enhances the reproducibility and transparency of the research.

Table 2: Depicts the used dataset Dermnet features, description and its importance

Feature	Description	Importance
Disease Classes	23 categories	Multi-class classification
Dataset Size	19,500 images	Improves model performance
Image Diversity	Clinical + Dermoscopic	Real-world robustness

4. Materials and Methodology:

To detect skin diseases at early stages, this research work proposes a hybrid model based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long short Term Memory (LSTM). The proposed workflow

of the hybrid model is shown in Figure 1. The workflow used the Image preprocessing steps, Holistically Nested Edge Detection (HNED), EfficientNetB0 for feature extraction and RMCNN-LSTM model for the classification of skin diseases.

Figure 1: Represents the workflow of the proposed hybrid model

4.1 Image Pre-processing for Skin Diseases Detection

The preprocessing in the proposed model depends on image resizing as a vital step. Thus, ensuring all input images are of the same size avoids distortion and enhances model accuracy. Initially, the images were of varied size; after resizing, the size of the images is 1024x 1024x 3. During resizing, preserving the aspect ratio is crucial to prevent changing the initial proportions of digital images. This is achieved by either adding zero values to the smaller dimension or truncating part of the larger dimension. Here, Bilinear interpolation is used for resizing the images. This method predicts the intensity value of each new pixel through a weighted average of the four closest pixels of the original image. Bilinear interpolation combines surrounding pixel values proportionally according to distance from the new pixel's location. Smoother transitions, fewer blocks, and more naturally appearing images after reshaping are the outcomes of this approach. For the DermNet dataset, bilinear interpolation is used to retain key visual elements, such as lesion borders, texture differences, and gradual color changes, which are crucial for proper feature extraction in deep learning.

$$BI'(a', b') = (1 - \delta a)(1 - \delta b)BI(a1, b1) + \delta a(1 - \delta b)BI(a2, b1) + (1 - \delta a)\delta bBI(a1, b2) + \delta a\delta bBI(a2, b2) \text{ --- (1)}$$

Where equation (1) represents:

(a, b) are the coordinates of the new pixel. ((a1, b1), (a2, b2) are the coordinates of the four nearest pixels. $BI(a1, b1), BI(a2, b1), BI(a1, b2), BI(a2, b2)$ are the pixel intensity values and δ is the relative distance factor that determines the new pixel value.

After image resizing noise reduction was done using Gaussian blurring. After resizing, a 3x3 kernel Gaussian Blur filter is used on the images. Gaussian Blur applies pixel value averaging with neighboring pixels, weighted by a Gaussian distribution, and smooths the image for a natural-appearing blur effect.

In our proposed methodology, for images of skin diseases, this filter plays a significant role in minimizing noise and undesired details, including hair strands, small illumination differences, or sensor-level noise, which may distract the deep learning model. While doing so, the larger structural patterns and textures like skin lesion boundaries, pigment variation, and shape anomaly, critical for proper skin condition classification, remain intact. Gaussian blurring for one one-dimensional function can be given as;

$$B(a) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{a^2}{2\sigma^2}} \text{-----(2)}$$

For two two-dimensional functions,

$$B(a, b) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{a^2+b^2}{2\sigma^2}} \text{----- (3)}$$

In equations (2) and (3), where a is the distance in the horizontal axis from the origin and b is the distance in the vertical axis from the origin, and σ is the standard deviation. In the proposed hybrid system, Gaussian blurring is applied as a preprocessing stage to the input images.

Next, Histogram equalization is utilized in our proposed method to standardize image contrast throughout the dataset such that disease patterns such as pigmentation, edges, and texture difference become more prominent. For example, a melanoma lesion usually contains fine differences in intensity and irregular boundary shapes that may be hidden in low-contrast images. Histogram equalization expands and redistributes pixel intensities over the complete span (0–255 for grayscale), brightening dark areas and flattening over-bright regions. This preprocessing enhances feature prominence and extracts more distinguishing patterns for precise classification. Mathematically for histogram equalization is represented in equation (4):

$$h_e = (L1) \cdot \sum_{j=0}^e \frac{n_j}{N} \text{.....(4)}$$

Where, h_e is the new intensity value after the equalization for gray scale e. L is the total number of possible intensity levels. n_j is the number of pixels with grey level j and N is the total number of pixels in the image. The equation (3) redistributes the pixel intensities so that the output histogram is uniform in nature.

In order to improve contrast and visual clarity of the skin images, Advanced Contrast Enhancement (CLAHE) has been incorporated into the proposed framework. CLAHE is one of the image processing techniques that adjusts contrast levels depending on local image statistics. The working model of the advanced constant enhancement technique is shown in Figure 2. It divides the image into small tiles and performs localized histogram equalization with a clipping limit, which prevents the over-amplification of noise.

Figure2: Working of CLAHE for contrast enhancement

Our proposed methodology used the sharpening technique to differentiate between the healthy and disease regions using sharpening techniques, thereby allowing for more accurate diagnosis of diseases. Consider an image SI , where SI is the sharpened image, I_a is the original pre-processed image, I_b is the Gaussian-blurred image, and α is the scaling factor. Here in our proposed work, the chosen value of α is 1.5. The equation (5) for Sharpened Images is represented as:

$$SI = I_a + \alpha (I_a - I_b) \text{-----(5)}$$

4.2 Image Segmentation for Skin Disease Detection

In this study, we implement a five-stage hybrid edge-aware segmentation framework that integrates classical image preprocessing with Holistically-Nested Edge Detection (HED). First, input images are subjected to grayscale conversion and Gaussian smoothing to suppress high-frequency noise. Second, adaptive global thresholding at $0.3 \times$ maximum intensity is applied, followed by morphological dilation and closing using an 11×11 elliptical structuring element to enhance structural continuity. Third, contour analysis is performed and the largest connected component is selected to define a region-of-interest (ROI), expanded by a 10-pixel margin to preserve contextual boundaries. Fourth, contrast enhancement is performed in HSV space with controlled scaling factors (Hue $\times 0.7$, Saturation $\times 1.5$, Value $\times 0.5$) followed by linear intensity adjustment ($\alpha = 1.5$, $\beta = 50$) to amplify edge saliency. Finally, enhanced images are processed using a five-stage VGG-based Holistically-Nested Edge Detection (HED) network, where side outputs from convolutional blocks (64, 128, 256, 512, 512 channels) are independently supervised and fused via a 1×1 convolution and sigmoid activation to generate high-resolution edge probability maps.

The novelty of HED lies in its deep supervision strategy and multi-scale side-output fusion, which enables simultaneous learning of fine and coarse edge representations, addressing gradient vanishing

issues common in deep networks and improving boundary localization accuracy compared to traditional single-scale edge detectors. The proposed work enhances edge detection robustness through structured ROI localization and input conditioning before deep inference, forming a hybrid preprocessing deep learning pipeline suitable for high-contrast boundary extraction tasks. Figure 3 shows the result of the image pre-processing techniques and Image segmentation on the Dermnet dataset.

Figure 3: Implementation of image preprocessing and image segmentation techniques on Dermnet dataset (image sample taken: Acne and Rosacea)

4.3 Feature Extraction

This algorithm performs deep feature extraction from skin disease images using EfficientNetB0 as a pretrained convolutional neural network. Each image is first loaded, resized to $224 \times 224 \times 3$, converted into a numerical array, and normalized so that it matches the format used during ImageNet training. After preprocessing, the image has the shape $(1, 224, 224, 3)$ and is passed into the EfficientNetB0 model without its final classification layer. The first stage, called the stem convolution, extracts basic visual patterns such as edges and colors and reduces the spatial size from $(224, 224, 3)$ to $(112, 112, 32)$. The data then flows through multiple MBConv (Mobile Inverted Bottleneck Convolution) blocks, which generate feature maps at different levels of abstraction. Inside each MBConv block, the feature map is first expanded in the channel dimension using a 1×1 convolution, allowing the network to learn richer representations. A depthwise convolution then captures spatial features like texture and shape, followed by a squeeze-and-excitation mechanism that highlights important channels and suppresses less useful ones. Finally, the feature map is projected back to a lower dimension, often with a residual connection to preserve important information.

Figure 4: Architecture of EfficientNet B0 for feature extraction

As the image moves through successive MBConv blocks, as shown in Figure 4, the feature maps gradually decrease in spatial size while increasing in depth, enabling hierarchical feature learning. For example, the transformations occur approximately as $(112, 112, 32) \rightarrow (112, 112, 16)$ for basic textures, $(112, 112, 16) \rightarrow (56, 56, 24)$ for local patterns, $(56, 56, 24) \rightarrow (28, 28, 40)$ for mid-level structures, $(28, 28, 40) \rightarrow (14, 14, 80)$ for shape-related features, $(14, 14, 80) \rightarrow (14, 14, 112)$ for enhanced semantic details, $(14, 14, 112) \rightarrow (7, 7, 192)$ for high-level representations, and finally $(7, 7, 192) \rightarrow (7, 7, 320)$ for highly discriminative features. A final convolution layer further expands this to a feature map of $(7, 7, 1280)$, which encodes rich information about the image such as lesion patterns, color variations, and structural irregularities. This 3D feature map is then passed through a Global Average Pooling layer, which converts it into a 1D feature vector of length 1280 by averaging each channel across the spatial dimensions. This vector serves as a compact and meaningful representation of the image. Finally, the feature vector is stored along with a corresponding numerical label (ranging from 0 to 22) based on the image's category, resulting in a dataset of feature vectors and labels that can be used for training classification models.

a. **Proposed Methodology:** This study proposes a hybrid deep learning framework based on a Recurrent Multiclass Convolutional Neural Network with Long Short-Term Memory (RMCNN–LSTM) for the automated classification of dermatological diseases using the Dermnet dataset. The proposed architecture, RMCNN–LSTM, couples the spatial feature extraction capability of CNNs with the sequential dependency modeling strength of LSTMs. The hybrid design seeks to model local and global patterns within the dermatological feature space. The overall network architecture is made up of stacked convolutional and pooling layers followed by recurrent layers and a multi-layer perceptron classifier. The following algorithm describes working of proposed hybrid model for achieving high training accuracy and loss.

ALGORITHM Train and Evaluate_RMCNN-LSTM

INPUT: CSV file "All_Feats_lbls.csv" containing features and label column

OUTPUT: Trained model file "rmcnn-lstm, Training Accuracy, Loss, Validation accuracy and loss

a. **IMPORT** libraries :

- a. numpy, pandas, matplotlib, seaborn
- b. sklearn : train_test_split, StandardScaler, metrics
- c. keras, tensorflow

b. **Load Dataset** : feature file as dataframe (output of PCA)

c. **Prepare features and lables**

d. **Split into train and test sets** :

`x_train, y_train, y_test ← train_test_split(x,y,test_size= 0.2, random_state=101`

e. **Normalize features:**

a. `Scaler ← StandardScaler()`

b. `x_train ← scaler.fit_transform(x_train)`

c. `x_test ← scaler.transform(x_test)`

f. **Reshape for Conv1D input**

a. Conv1D expects shape: (samples, steps, channels)

b. `X_train ← reshape(X_train, (num_train_samples, num_features, 1))`

c. `X_test ← reshape(X_test, (num_test_samples, num_features, 1))`

g. **ONE-HOT encode labels**

a. `num_classes ← 23`

b. `y_train_ohe ← to_categorical(y_train, num_classes)`

c. `y_test_ohe ← to_categorical(y_test, num_classes)`

h. **Build hybrid model**

`model ← Sequential()`

- **CNN block 1**

`model.add(Conv1D(filters=64, kernel_size=3, activation='relu',`

`input_shape=(num_features, 1)))`

`model.add(MaxPooling1D(pool_size=2))`

`model.add(BatchNormalization())`

`model.add(Dropout(0.3))`

- **CNN block 2**

`model.add(Conv1D(filters=128, kernel_size=3, activation='relu'))`

`model.add(MaxPooling1D(pool_size=2))`

`model.add(BatchNormalization())`

`model.add(Dropout(0.3))`

- **Prepare for LSTM**

```
model.add(Reshape((-1, 128)))
```

- LSTM block

```
model.add(LSTM(200, return_sequences=True))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))
model.add(LSTM(100, return_sequences=False))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))
```
- Dense classifier

```
model.add(Dense(256, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
model.add(Dense(128, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
model.add(Dense(num_classes, activation='softmax'))
```
- i. Compile model

```
Optimizer <- Adam (learning_rate= 0.01)
Model.compile( optimizer= optimizer, loss= ' categorical_crossentropy', metrics= [' accuracy'])
```
- j. Set early stopping

```
early_stopping <- EarlyStopping(monitor= ' val_loss', patience=5, restore_best_weights=True)
```
- k. Train Model

```
history <- model.fit(
  X_train, y_train_oh,
  epochs=100,
  batch_size=32,
  validation_data=(X_test, y_test_oh),
  shuffle=True,
  callbacks=[early_stopping]
)
```
- l. model.save
- m. EVALUATE model on test set

```
loss, accuracy <- model.evaluate(X_test, y_test_oh)
print loss and accuracy
```

End

Figure 5: Proposed architecture of convolutional neural network (CNN)

In the proposed model, as shown in Figure 5, a one-dimensional convolutional layer (Conv1D) comprising 64 filters with a kernel size of 3 is followed by the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. This layer is responsible for extracting local patterns by applying convolutional kernels across the input sequence, thereby capturing short-range relationships among neighboring features. Subsequently, a MaxPooling1D layer with a pool size of 2 is applied to reduce the feature dimensionality by half, which helps in lowering computational complexity and introducing translation invariance. A Batch Normalization layer is then used to normalize the activations within each mini-batch, improving training stability and convergence speed. To further prevent overfitting, a Dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 is incorporated, randomly disabling a portion of neurons during training.

The second convolutional block increases the number of filters to 128 while retaining the same kernel size of 3. This block follows a similar structure, including convolution, max-pooling, batch normalization, and dropout layers. The deeper architecture enables the model to learn more complex and abstract feature representations. The output from this block, represented as $((L, 128))$, where (L) denotes the reduced sequence length after pooling, is reshaped using a $\text{Reshape}((-1, 128))$ layer. This transformation allows the convolutional features to be interpreted as a sequence of feature vectors, making them suitable for temporal modeling by LSTM layers.

figure 6: Architecture of proposed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

As shown in Figure 6, the sequential learning component consists of two stacked LSTM layers. The first LSTM layer contains 200 units and is configured with `return_sequences=True`, allowing it to pass

the entire sequence output to the next LSTM layer. The second LSTM layer, with 100 units, outputs only the final hidden state (`return_sequences=False`), which serves as a compact representation of the learned sequence. Dropout with a rate of 0.3 is applied between the LSTM layers to enhance generalization and prevent overfitting. This recurrent architecture effectively captures long-range dependencies and contextual relationships that are not addressed by convolutional layers alone.

Following the LSTM layers, the extracted features are passed through fully connected (Dense) layers for classification. Two dense layers with 256 and 128 neurons, respectively, are employed, both using ReLU activation to learn high-level feature representations. Dropout with a rate of 0.5 is applied after each dense layer to further reduce overfitting. Finally, the output layer consists of 23 neurons corresponding to the different skin disease classes, and uses a SoftMax activation function to produce a probability distribution over all classes.

The proposed model RMCNN_LSTM was compiled using the Adam optimizer. A learning rate of 0.001 was used based on empirical experimentation. The categorical cross-entropy loss function was employed to measure the divergence between predicted probabilities and true one-hot encoded labels, ensuring the optimization process minimizes the discrepancy across all classes simultaneously. The model was trained for a maximum of 100 epochs with a mini-batch size of 32, employing early stopping as a regularization strategy. The early stopping mechanism monitors the validation loss during training and automatically halts the process if no improvement is observed over five consecutive epochs (`patience=5`).

5 Experimental Setup

The proposed model was implemented on the Python platform using Jupyter notebook on the Dermnet dataset containing a total of 19500 image samples, which is divided into 80% for training and 20% for testing. After training the model, the training accuracy and training loss were evaluated with performance metrics based on the parameters of the confusion matrix: True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN), as shown in Figure 7.

		Predicted Values	
		Positive	Negative
Actual Values	Positive	True Positive	False Negative
	Negative	False Positive	True Negative

Figure 7: Shows the parameters TP, TN, FP, and FN of confusion matrix

The classification metrics are:

a. Accuracy : $ACC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$ -----(6)

b. Precision: $Pre = \frac{TP}{Tp+FP}$ ----- (7)

c. Recall: $Rec = \frac{TP}{Tp+FN}$ ----- (8)

d. F1- Score = $F1 - score = 2 X \frac{Pre \times Rec}{Pre+Rec}$ ----- (9)

e. Specificity $Spec = \frac{TN}{TN+FP}$ ----- (10)

5.1 Outcome:

Figure 8: (a) Training and validation accuracy (b) Training and validation loss

Figure 8 (a) shows the training and validation accuracy, and for each training sample, the model predicts one of the 23 classes, and if the predicted class matches the true class, it is counted as correct. Figure 6 (b) shows the training and validation loss. Here loss function, categorical cross-entropy, was used to calculate the error between actual and predicted diseases.

From the above discussed experimental setup, it is observed that the hybrid model provides the training accuracy 94%, training loss 20%, validation accuracy 80% and validation loss 80%. The validation accuracy achieved by the model is with the help of the Adam optimizer, using a categorical cross-entropy loss function. From the results, it is observed that the training accuracy and loss percentage is 80% and 51%, which require an increase in training accuracy and a reduction in training loss.

6 Conclusion

In this study, a proposed hybrid model RMCNN-LSTM, was implemented. The model uses the deep learning-based Holistically nested edge detection to detect edges in detail in image segmentation and EfficientNet Bo feature extraction. A total of 1280 features were extracted from the image. Further, these extracted features were employed to Proposed hybrid Model RMCNN-LSTM, to evaluate the training accuracy and loss and validation accuracy and loss. From the result outcomes, it is noticed that the archived training accuracy 94%, training loss 20%, validation accuracy 80% and validation loss 80%. The research highlights the sophisticated use of deep learning methodologies to detect skin diseases at early stages. Further, in the future, this research work tends to increase training and validation accuracy and decrease training and validation loss.

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